

The first combined checklist of earthworms of the Northeastern Mediterranean region (Clitellata: Megadrili)

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Abstract. The first combined checklist of earthworms of the Balkan Peninsula, Anatolia, the Levant and Cyprus is presented. Out of the 226 taxa, 216 belong to the Holarctic family Lumbricidae. Ten further species are from the families Criodrilidae, Acanthodrilidae, Ocnodrilidae and Megascolecidae. The widely introduced peregrine species take part with 11.9% (27 taxa). The number of endemics within the studied areas is highest on the Balkan Peninsula (90 taxa). As a result of this study, four synonyms were found, and the subgenus *Trapezonscolex* Qiu & Bouché, 1998 was raised to genus level for the former Turkish *Eophila* species *Eo. cavazzutii cavazzutii* Omodeo, 1988 and *Eo. cavazzutii pascuorum* Omodeo, 1988.

Keywords. Northeastern Mediterranean, Oligochaeta, species list, Lumbricidae, Megascolecidae, Acanthodrilidae.

INTRODUCTION

The Balkan Peninsula is a relatively well-defined area of Europe. The Black, the Aegean and the Ionian Sea bound it from the eastern, southern and western directions respectively. However, drawing its northern border is quite difficult, the different authors share different concepts (Griffiths *et al.* 2004, Mahunka *et al.* 2013). One possible way as proposed here, is to take the valley of the Siret River, the southern border of the Southern Carpathians, the Danube, the Sava, the northern projection of the Dinaric Alps, and the Ćicarija and Učka Mts.

The zoological peculiarities of the Balkans provoked attention as early as the beginning of the 20th century and resulted in intensive researches on the area regarding earthworms as well (Cognetti 1906, Černosvitov 1930). After this long-lasting work covering a whole century, one could conceive that the earthworm fauna of the Balkan Peninsula is well-known, but it is important to emphasize that our knowledge on the Balkan countries are quite different, as the monograph of Mršić (1991) reflects it well.

Without any doubt, the former Yugoslav countries are the most well-known areas of the Balkan regarding its earthworm fauna (*e.g.* Karaman 1972a, Šapkarev 1972a, Karaman & Stojanović 1996, Stojanović & Milutinović 2013, Szederjesi 2013a, Trakić *et al.* 2016, Stojanović *et al.* 2017a).

Greece (Zicsi & Michalis 1981, Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012a, Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a) and Bulgaria (Černosvitov 1934a, Zicsi & Csuzdi 1986, Valchovski 2012, Szederjesi 2013b) are also intensively studied, but there are still huge unexplored areas in the above mentioned countries.

The Albanian earthworm researches are most recent (Dhora 2010, Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b, 2015).

According to the Balkan definition proposed here, the most southern part of Romania also belongs to the Balkan Peninsula, including the Romanian part of Dobruja and the area lying from the southern part of the Carpathians to the Danube. We have only sporadic data from this region (Pop 1949), however two species – *Cernosvitovia dobrogeana* (Pop, 1938) and *C. munteni-ana* Zicsi & Pop, 1991 – were described from

here. The European part of Turkey also belongs to the Balkan, the earthworm fauna of this area is lesser known (Valchovski & Mısırlıoğlu 2017).

Anatolia or Asia Minor forms a large part of Turkey. The Black and the Aegean Sea bound it from the northern and western directions. The Mediterranean Sea, the Taurus Mts and Upper Mesopotamia borders it from south, while the Greater and Lesser Caucasus bound it from north-east and east. The Bosphorus, the Marmara Sea and the Dardanelles separate it from the Balkan Peninsula.

The first organized earthworm collecting trip to Turkey took place at the end of the 1980's and resulted in describing altogether 15 species new to science (Omodeo & Rota 1989, 1991). Csuzdi *et al.* (2006) summarized the knowledge on the Turkish earthworm fauna. Since then, the investigations are more or less continuous (Mısırlıoğlu 2008, 2010, 2012, Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2017, Szederjesi *et al.* 2014a, Szederjesi & Mısırlıoğlu 2017).

Pavliček *et al.* (2007) defines the Levant as "circa 150 km wide area between the Mediterranean Sea and the Syrian and Arabian deserts. The Taurus Mts borders it from north and the Isthmus of Suez from south".

The earthworm researches in the Levant began at the end of the 19th century (Rosa 1893a, Michaelsen 1901) and continued in the 20th century (Černosvitov 1938a, Omodeo 1956, Zicsi 1985a). The recent studies mainly focused on Israel (Csuzdi & Pavliček 1999, 2002, Szederjesi *et al.* 2013a) and Jordan (Csuzdi & Pavliček 2005b, Pavliček & Csuzdi 2006a, Szederjesi *et al.* 2013b).

We have only scarce information on the earthworms of the Aegean islands, most data are sporadic (Cognetti 1906, 1913, Michaelsen 1928, Černosvitov 1934b). The first overview on the Cretan earthworm fauna is from Szederjesi (2017).

Cyprus is the third largest island of the Mediterranean Sea. Its wildlife is species rich, nonetheless we didn't have any information on its

earthworm fauna until the 1990's (Michalis 1993) and 2000's (Pavliček & Csuzdi 2006b, 2008). Szederjesi *et al.* (2016) described the first endemic earthworm species from the island. According to Pavliček & Csuzdi (2017), the origin of the earthworm fauna of Cyprus probably goes back to the Messinian Salinity Crisis Period, when three, now submerged land bridges – the Misis, Hecatanus and Latakia – connected the island to the Bay of Iskenderun and Syria, due to the lowering of the Mediterranean sea level.

The aim of this paper is to summarise our recent knowledge and present the first checklist of the earthworms of the Balkan Peninsula, Anatolia, Levant and the Aegean Islands *aka* the North-eastern Mediterranean region.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The data were collected by screening the available literature. The valid species names are given according to the online database of Csuzdi (2012). In the synonymy list, the original combination of names together with references to the present usage are presented for all species. The comprehensive works of Mršić (1991), Pavliček *et al.* (2003), Pavliček & Csuzdi (2006b), Valchovski (2012), Csuzdi *et al.* (2006) and Szederjesi *et al.* (2017a) are regarded as a basis and only the references published after these works are given.

LIST OF SPECIES

Family Lumbricidae Rafinesque-Schmaltz, 1815

Genus *Allolobophora* Eisen, 1874

Allolobophora altimontana Mršić, 1982

Allolobophora altimontana Mršić, 1982: 58.
Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 3.

Karpatodinariona altimontana: Mršić 1991: 245.
Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Distribution. Slovenia, Croatia (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Allolobophora brunnecephala* Kvavadze, 1985**

Allolobophora brunnecephala Kvavadze, 1985: 201. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 2. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

?*Allolobophora smaragdina*: Omodeo & Rota 1989: 182. (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006)

?*Allolobophora bellicosa*: Omodeo & Rota 1991: 177. (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006)

Distribution. Turkey, Georgia (Kvavadze 1985, Csuzdi *et al.* 2006)

***Allolobophora bulgarica* Černosvitov, 1934**

Allolobophora bulgarica Černosvitov, 1934a: 74. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 254.

Cernosvitovia (Cernosvitovia) bulgarica: Mršić 1991: 144.

Cernosvitovia bulgarica: Valchovski 2012: 90. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10.; 2013: 639.

Distribution. Bulgaria (Valchovski 2012).

Remarks. Zicsi (1981a) and Mršić (1991) provisionally placed this species to *Cernosvitovia* however, Zicsi & Pop (1991: 126) examining the type specimen revealed that its male pore is located on segment 15 therefore *bulgarica* belongs to the genus *Allolobophora*.

***Allolobophora carneluttii* Mršić, 1990**

Allolobophora (Serbiona) carneluttii Mršić, 1990: 58. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 254.

Serbiona carneluttii: Mršić 1991: 201. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Distribution. Serbia (Stojanović *et al.* 2008).

***Allolobophora chlorotica chlorotica* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion chloroticum Savigny, 1826: 182.

Allolobophora chlorotica: Šapkarev 2001: 100. Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 456. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 2. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Dhora 2010: 82. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9.; 2013: 639.

Allolobophora chlorotica chlorotica: Mršić 1991: 211. Csuzdi & Pavliček 2005b: 88. Valchovski 2012: 87.; 2014: 2. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 3. Stojanović &

Milutinović 2013: 148.; 2014: 308. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 180. Szedlerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 58. Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003: 50 (for complete synonymy).

Distribution. widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Allolobophora cryptocystis* (Černosvitov, 1935)**

Eophila cryptocystis Černosvitov, 1935a: 265.

Microeophila cryptocystis: Mršić 1991: 223. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Allolobophora cryptocystis: Csuzdi 2012.

Distribution. Bosnia-Herzegovina (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora demirkapiae* Karaman, 1969**

Allolobophora demirkapiae Karaman, 1969: 80. Szedlerjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 260. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 254.

Italobalkaniona demirkapiae: Mršić 1991: 163. Šapkarev 1997: 103.

Distribution. Macedonia, Albania (Szedlerjesi & Csuzdi 2012b).

***Allolobophora dofleini* (Ude, 1922)**

Helodrilus (Allolobophora) dofleini Ude, 1922: 157.

Allolobophora dofleini: Trakić *et al.* 2016: 254. Szedlerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 58. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 180.; 2017b: 138.

Serbiona dofleini: Mršić, 1991: 180. Šapkarev 1997: 104.; 2001: 100.

Distribution. Serbia, Macedonia, Greece (Szedlerjesi *et al.* 2017a).

***Allolobophora immaculata* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Allolobophora immaculata Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 181. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 2. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Allolobophora jonesapcarevi* (Blakemore, 2004)**

Allolobophora udei Šapkarev, 1972: 120.

Serbiona udei: Mršić 1991: 184.

Serbiona joncesapcarevi Blakemore, 2004: 78. (nom. nov.)

Allolobophora joncesapcarevi: Csuzdi 2012. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 255.

Distribution. Macedonia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora josapi* Blakemore, 2006**

Allolobophora dofleini udei Šapkarev, 1991: 52.; 1997: 104.

Allolobophora josapi Blakemore, 2006: 5. (nom. nov.), Trakić *et al.* 2016: 255.

Distribution. Macedonia (Šapkarev 1991).

***Allolobophora kosowensis* Karaman, 1968**

Allolobophora kosowensis Karaman, 1968: 50.

Serbiona kosowensis kosowensis: Mršić 1991: 191. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Eophila kosowensis: Šapkarev 2002: 304.

Allolobophora kosowensis kosowensis: Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308. Milutinović *et al.* 2015: 473. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 255. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 180. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 58.

Allolobophora kosowensis montenegrina Šapkarev, 1975a: 33. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 148. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 255. **syn. nov.**

Serbiona kosowensis montenegrina: Mršić 1991: 192. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Distribution. Serbia, Montenegro, Greece (Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a).

Remarks. *A. kosowensis kosowensis* was described without having tubercles but, according to the original description the worms were not fully adult ("Der Clitellus ist schwach entwickelt" = slightly developed). Later, Šapkarev (1975a) described the subspecies *kosowensis montenegrina* with the same clitellar position as for the typical subspecies but tubercles on 44–50, 51. Until *kosowensis kosowensis* possessed spermathecae, they were lacking in *k. montenegrina*. Mršić (1991) questioned the lack of tubercles in *A. kosowensis kosowensis* and wrote that *kosowensis montenegrina* has spermathecae in 10, 11 (same as in the typical form). Therefore morphologically the two subspecies are completely identical but represent different developmental stages.

***Allolobophora leoni* Michaelsen, 1891**

Allolobophora leoni Michaelsen, 1891: 15. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 4. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Valchovski 2012: 87. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9.; 2013: 639.; 2017a: 180. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308.

Pannoniona leoni: Mršić 1991: 227.

Distribution. Central-Europe and the eastern shore of the Black Sea (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Allolobophora macedonica* Šapkarev, 1977**

Eophila macedonica Šapkarev, 1977a: 91.

Italobalkaniona macedonica: Mršić 1991: 166. Šapkarev 1997: 103.

Allolobophora macedonica: Csuzdi 2012. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 256.

Distribution. Macedonia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora matjasici* Mršić, 1990**

Allolobophora (Serbiona) matjasici Mršić, 1990: 57.

Serbiona matjasici: Mršić 1991: 199. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Allolobophora matjasici: Trakić *et al.* 2016: 256.

Distribution. Serbia (Stojanović *et al.* 2008).

***Allolobophora mayeri* Mršić, 1990**

Allolobophora (Serbiona) mayeri Mršić, 1990: 56.

Serbiona mayeri: Mršić 1991: 203. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Allolobophora mayeri: Trakić *et al.* 2016: 256.

Distribution. Bosnia-Herzegovina (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora mehadiensis mehadiensis* Rosa, 1895**

Allolobophora mehadiensis Rosa, 1895: 3. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9.

Serbiona mehadiensis mehadiensis: Mršić 1991: 185. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Valchovski 2012: 98.

Serbiona pannonica (Cognetti, 1906): Mršić 1991: 198. Šapkarev 1997: 104. (Csuzdi 2012)

Allolobophora mehadiensis mehadiensis: Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308.

Distribution. Hungary, Romania, Serbia, Bulgaria (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003, Valchovski 2012).

***Allolobophora mehadiensis boscaiui* Pop, 1948**

Allolobophora mehadiensis boscaiui Pop, 1948
Serbiona mehadiensis boscaiui: Mršić 1991: 187. Šapkarev 1997: 104.
Allolobophora mehadiensis voivodinensis Šapkarev, 1989: 40. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308. (Szederjesi *et al.* 2014b)
Serbiona mehadiensis voivodinensis: Mršić 1991: 189. Šapkarev 1997: 104.
Allolobophora mehadiensis boscaiui: Szederjesi *et al.* 2014b: 86.

Distribution. Romania, Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora paratuleskovi* Šapkarev, 1975**

Allolobophora paratuleskovi Šapkarev, 1975b: 55. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 256. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 180.
Serbiona paratuleskovi: Mršić 1991: 206. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Distribution. Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora pyrenaicoides* (Šapkarev, 1977)**

Eophila pyrenaicoides Šapkarev, 1977a: 75.
Italobalkaniona pyrenaicoides: Mršić 1991: 162. Šapkarev 1997: 103.
Allolobophora pyrenaicoides: Csuzdi 2012. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 256.

Distribution. Macedonia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora robusta robusta* Rosa, 1895**

Allolobophora robusta Rosa, 1895: 2.
Serbiona robusta robusta: Mršić 1991: 162. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Stojanović & Karaman 2007: 23. Valchovski 2012: 99. Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 639.
Allolobophora robusta robusta: Szederjesi 2013a: 62. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308.

Distribution. Romania, Bulgaria, Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora robusta spasenijakaramani* (Blakemore, 2004)**

Allolobophora robusta serbica Karaman, 1983: 52.
Serbiona robusta serbica: Mršić 1991: 162. Šapkarev 1997: 104.
Serbiona spasenijakaramani Blakemore, 2004: 78. (nom.nov.)
Allolobophora robusta spasenijakaramani: Csuzdi 2012. Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 639.
Allolobophora spasenijakaramani: Trakić *et al.* 2016: 257. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 181.

Distribution. Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora ruzsai* Szederjesi, 2014**

Allolobophora ruzsai Szederjesi, 2014: 48. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 256.

Distribution. Montenegro (Szederjesi 2014).

***Allolobophora serbica* (Šapkarev, 1977)**

Eophila serbica Šapkarev, 1977a: 93.
Serbiona serbica: Mršić 1991: 162. Šapkarev 1997: 104.
Allolobophora serbica: Csuzdi 2012. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 181.

Distribution. Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora speciosa* Mršić & Šapkarev, 1987**

Eophila speciosa Mršić & Šapkarev, 1987: 69.
Serbiona speciosa: Mršić 1991: 202. Šapkarev 1997: 104.
Allolobophora speciosa: Csuzdi 2012. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 257.

Distribution. Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora stankovici* (Šapkarev, 1971)**

Allolobophora januaeargenti stankovici Šapkarev, 1971: 152.
Italobalkaniona stankovici: Mršić 1991: 165. Šapkarev 1997: 103.
Allolobophora stankovici: Csuzdi 2012. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 257.

Distribution. Macedonia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora strumicae* Šapkarev, 1973**

- Allolobophora dofleini strumicae* Šapkarev, 1973: 44.
Serbiona strumicae: Mršić 1991: 183. Šapkarev 1997: 104.
Allolobophora strumicae: Csuzdi 2012. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 257.

Distribution. Macedonia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora sturanyi sturanyi* Rosa, 1895**

- Allolobophora sturanyi* Rosa, 1895: 5.
Karpatodinariona sturanyi: Mršić 1991: 250. Stojanović *et al.* 2008: 59.
Allolobophora sturanyi sturanyi: Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 5. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 148. Szedzerjesi 2013a: 62.

Distribution. Croatia, Serbia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Montenegro (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora sturanyi dacica* (Pop, 1938)**

- Eophila dacica* Pop, 1938: 142.
Karpatodinariona dacica: Mršić 1991: 246.
Allolobophora sturanyi dacica: Csuzdi & Pop 2008: 26.

Distribution. Hungary, Romania, Moldova, Serbia, Bosnia-Herzegovina and Croatia (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Allolobophora treskavicensis* (Mršić, 1991)**

- Italobalkaniona treskavicensis* Mršić, 1991: 165. Šapkarev 1997: 103.
Allolobophora treskavicensis: Csuzdi 2012. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 257.

Distribution. Macedonia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora tuleskovi* (Černosvitov, 1937)**

- Eophila tuleskovi* Černosvitov, 1937a: 87.
Serbiona tuleskovi: Mršić 1991: 205. Šapkarev 1997: 104.
Serbiona tuleskovi: Valchovski 2012: 99. (sic!)
Allolobophora tuleskovi: Csuzdi 2012. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 258.

Distribution. Bulgaria (Valchovski 2012).

***Allolobophora yugoslavica* (Šapkarev, 1977)**

- Eophila yugoslavica* Šapkarev, 1977a: 89.
Serbiona yugoslavica: Mršić 1991: 196. Šapkarev 1997: 104.
Allolobophora yugoslavica: Csuzdi 2012. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 258.

Distribution. Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Allolobophora zicsi* Šapkarev, 1975**

- Allolobophora zicsi* Šapkarev, 1975c: 44. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 258.
non *Allolobophora zicsii* Bouché, 1972: 424.
Allolobophora orahovacensis Reynolds & Cook 1976: 148. (nom. nov.)
Allolobophora sapkarevi Easton, 1983: 486. (nom. nov.)
Italobalkaniona zicsii: Mršić 1991: 168. Šapkarev 1997: 103. (sic!)

Distribution. Serbia (Mršić 1991).

Remarks. There are some confusion in the literature regarding the name *Allolobophora zicsi* Šapkarev, 1975. Bouché (1972) described a species *Allolobophora* (s.l.) *zicsii* from France. Here the epithet is clearly a genitive and is formed correctly from a modern personal name (Zicsi) (ICZN Art. 31.1.2). Later, Šapkarev (1975) described *Allolobophora zicsi*, here the epithet is clearly a noun in apposition and also correct according to ICZN (Art. 31.1.1) and does not fall in homonymy (ICZN Art. 31.1.3 and example). Therefore the names *A. orahovacensis* Reynolds and Cook, 1976 and the later *A. sapkarevi* Easton, 1983 are unnecessary replacement names.

Genus *Aporrectodea* Örley, 1885

***Aporrectodea caliginosa caliginosa* Savigny, 1826**

- Enterion caliginosum* Savigny, 1826: 180.
Allolobophora (*Allolobophora*) *caliginosa*: Rosa 1893a: 7.
Allolobophora caliginosa caliginosa: Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 141.
Aporrectodea (*Aporrectodea*) *caliginosa caliginosa*: Mršić 1991: 321.
Aporrectodea caliginosa: Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2005a: 71.; 2005b: 88. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006a: 183.; 2006b: S114.; 2008: 193.; 2017: 592. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 4. (part.). Mısırlıoğlu

2009: 22. (part.). Dhora 2010: 82. Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 639.; 2017a: 181. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 5. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 149.; 2014: 308. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013a: 392.; 2013b: 201.; 2014a: 556 (part.). Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2015: 111.

Aporrectodea caliginosa caliginosa: Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 456. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 56. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9. Valchovski 2012: 88.; 2014: 2. Szederjesi 2014: 49. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 59.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Aporrectodea caliginosa trapezoides* (Dugès, 1828)**

Lumbricus trapezoides Dugès, 1828: 289.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) caliginosa trapezoides: Mršić 1991: 328.

Aporrectodea caliginosa trapezoides: Šapkarev 2001: 111. Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 456. Valchovski 2012: 88.; 2014: 3. Szederjesi *et al.* 2016.; 2017a: 60.

Aporrectodea trapezoides: Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9.; 2013: 639.; 2017a: 182. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 8. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 151.; 2014: 308.

Aporrectodea caliginosa (part.): Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 4.; 2007: 348. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013b: 91.; 2014a: 556.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Aporrectodea cemernicensis* Mršić, 1991**

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) cemernicensis Mršić, 1991: 284. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Aporrectodea cemernicensis: Szederjesi 2013a: 63. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 258.

Distribution. Bosnia-Herzegovina, Serbia (Szederjesi 2013a).

***Aporrectodea dinarica* (Mršić, 1987)**

Meroandriella dinarica Mršić, 1987a: 2.; 1991: 340. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Aporrectodea dinarica: Csuzdi 2012. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 258.

Distribution. Slovenia (Mršić 1991).

***Aporrectodea dubiosa* (Örley, 1881)**

Criodrilus dubiosus Örley, 1881: 603.

Allolobophora dubiosa: Šapkarev 2002: 296.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) dubiosa dubiosa: Mršić 1991: 334.

Aporrectodea dubiosa dubiosa: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 4. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Aporrectodea dubiosa: Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9. Valchovski 2012: 88. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 6. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308.

Distribution. From Slovakia to the shore of the Black Sea, and its eastern shore (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Aporrectodea georgii* (Michaelsen, 1890)**

Allolobophora georgii Michaelsen, 1890: 3.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) georgii: Mršić 1991: 315.

Aporrectodea georgii: Dhora 2010: 82. Milutinović *et al.* 2010: 629. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9.; 2017a: 181. Valchovski 2012: 89. Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 262. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 6. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 149. Szederjesi 2013a: 63.; Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 60.

Distribution. widely distributed Atlanto-Mediterranean species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Aporrectodea handlirschi handlirschi* (Rosa, 1897)**

Allolobophora handlirschi Rosa, 1897: 3.

Eiseniona handlirschi rhenani: Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 23.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) handlirschi: Mršić 1991: 292.

Aporrectodea handlirschi handlirschi: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 4. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Stojanović *et al.* 2008: 59. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 60.

Aporrectodea handlirschi: Valchovski 2012: 89. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9.; 2013: 639.; 2017a:

181. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 6. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 150. Szederjesi 2013a: 63.

Distribution. from Italy and Poland to the Caucasus (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Aporrectodea handlirschi mahnerti* (Zicsi, 1973)**

Allolobophora handlirschi mahnerti Zicsi, 1973: 230. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 6. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Szederjesi *et al.* 2014a: 557.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Aporrectodea jassyensis* (Michaelsen, 1891)**

Allolobophora jassyensis Michaelsen, 1891: 15. *Allolobophora (Allolobophora) jassyensis*: Rosa 1893a: 8.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) jassyensis: Mršić 1991: 316. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Aporrectodea jassyensis jassyensis: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 6. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Valchovski 2012: 89.; 2014: 3.

Aporrectodea jassyensis: Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 456. Csuzdi & Pavliček 2005a: 72.; 2005b: 89. Csuzdi *et al.* 2007: 349. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Dhora 2010: 82. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9.; 2013: 639.; 2017a: 181. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 7. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 150.; 2014: 308. Szederjesi 2013b: 77.; Szederjesi *et al.* 2013b: 202.; 2014a: 557.; 2017a: 61. Valchovski & Szederjesi 2016: 357. Pavliček & Csuzdi 2017: 593.

Distribution. Widely distributed Trans-Aegean species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Aporrectodea macvensis* (Šapkarev, 2002)**

Allolobophora macvensis Šapkarev, 2002: 299.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) macvensis: Mršić 1991: 294. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Aporrectodea macvensis: Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 258. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 181.

Distribution. Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Aporrectodea longa* (Ude, 1885)**

Allolobophora longa Ude, 1885: 136.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) longa: Mršić 1991: 330. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9. Valchovski 2012: 90. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 61.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species of Atlantic origin (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Aporrectodea rosea* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion roseum Savigny, 1826: 182.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) rosea rosea: Mršić 1991: 296.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) rosea balcanica: Mršić 1991: 303. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) rosea bimastoides: Mršić 1991: 304.

Aporrectodea rosea: Šapkarev 2001: 111. Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 456. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 55.; 2005a: 128. Csuzdi & Pavliček 2005a: 72.; 2005b: 89. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 6. Pavliček & Csuzdi 2006a: 184.; 2006b: S114.; 2008: 193.; 2017: 592. Csuzdi *et al.* 2007: 349. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Dhora 2010: 82. Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 262. Stojanović *et al.* 2012:9.; 2013: 639.; 2017a: 182. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 7. Szederjesi 2013a: 64. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 150.; 2014: 308. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013a: 392.; 2013b: 202.; 2014a: 557.; 2017a: 61. Valchovski & Szederjesi 2016: 357.

Allolobophora rosea balcanica: Šapkarev 2002: 296.

Aporrectodea rosea rosea: Valchovski 2012: 90.; 2014: 3.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Aporrectodea sineporis* (Omodeo, 1952)**

Eiseniella balcanica sine-poris Omodeo, 1952: 31.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) sineporis: Mršić 1991: 287.

Aporrectodea sineporis: Stojanović & Karaman 2005b: 133. Milutinović *et al.* 2010: 629. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 8. Szederjesi 2013a: 64. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 182.

Distribution. Italy, Austria, Hungary, Slovenia, Serbia (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003, Stojanović & Karaman 2005b).

***Aporrectodea smaragdina* (Rosa, 1892)**

Allolobophora smaragdina Rosa, 1892: 1. Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 139.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) smaragdina: Mršić 1991: 308.

Aporrectodea smaragdina: Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 55. Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 263.; 2015: 112. Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 639.; 2017a: 182. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 8. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 150. Szedzerjesi 2013a: 65.; 2014: 49.

Aporrectodea (Aporrectodea) smaragdinoides Šapkarev, 1989: 42.; 1997: 104. Mršić 1991: 312. (Szedzerjesi 2013a).

Distribution. From Italy to Serbia (Mršić 1991).

Genus *Bimastos* Moore, 1891

***Bimastos eiseni* (Levinsen, 1884)**

Lumbricus eiseni Levinsen, 1884: 241.

Eisenia eiseni: Karaman & Stojanović 2002: 224. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 57.

Allolobophoridella eiseni: Mršić 1991: 255. Dhora 2010: 82. Valchovski 2012: 87. Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 262; 2015: 111. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 9.; 2013: 639. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 5. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 149. Szedzerjesi 2014: 49. Valchovski & Szedzerjesi 2016: 356. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 59.

Bimastos eiseni: Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 140. Csuzdi *et al.* 2017: 13.

Distribution. Peregrine species of North American origin (Csuzdi *et al.* 2017).

***Bimastos parvus* (Eisen, 1874)**

Allolobophora parva Eisen, 1874: 46.

Bimastos parvus: Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 455. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006a: 184. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2013b: 202, Csuzdi *et al.* 2017: 19.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species of North American origin (Pavlíček *et al.* 2003).

***Bimastos rubidus* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion rubidum Savigny, 1826: 182.

Dendrobaena rubida rubida: Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 140.

Dendrobaena rubida tenuis: Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 140.

Dendrodrilus rubidus rubidus: Mršić 1991: 263. Šapkarev 2001: 111. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 57.; 2005a: 130. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10.; 2013: 639.; 2017a: 184. Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 269.; 2015: 112. Valchovski 2012: 93. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 12. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 154.; 2014: 308. Szedzerjesi 2013a: 69.; 2014: 50. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2014a: 565.; 2017a: 66. Valchovski & Szedzerjesi 2016: 357.

Dendrodrilus rubidus tenuis: Mršić 1991: 270. Šapkarev 2001: 111. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 56.; 2005a: 130. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10.; 2017a: 184. Valchovski 2012: 94.

Dendrodrilus rubidus subrubicundus: Mršić 1991: 267. Šapkarev 2001: 111. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2008: 194.; 2017: 592. Dhora 2010: 82. Valchovski 2012: 93. Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 269. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10.; 2013: 639.; 2017a: 184. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 12. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 154.; 2014: 308. Szedzerjesi 2013a: 69.; 2014: 50.; Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2016.; 2017a: 67.

Dendrodrilus rubidus subrubicunda: Karaman & Stojanović 2002: 224.

Bimastos rubidus: Csuzdi *et al.* 2017: 20.

Distribution. Peregrine species of North American origin (Csuzdi *et al.* 2017).

Genus *Cernosvitovia* Omodeo, 1956

***Cernosvitovia biserialis* (Černosvitov, 1937)**

Allolobophora biserialis Černosvitov, 1937a: 85.

Cernosvitovia (Cernosvitovia) biserialis: Mršić 1991: 142. Šapkarev 1997: 103.; 2002: 300.

Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10.; 2013: 639. Valchovski 2012: 90.
Cernosvitovia biserialis: Trakić *et al.* 2016: 258.

Distribution. Serbia, Bulgaria (Mršić 1991).

***Cernosvitovia dobrogeana* (Pop, 1938)**

Octolasion dobrogeanum Pop, 1938: 148.
Cernosvitovia (*Cernosvitovia*) *dobrogeana*: Mršić 1991: 144. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10. Valchovski 2012: 90.
Cernosvitovia dobrogeana: Trakić *et al.* 2016: 259.

Distribution. Romania, Bulgaria (Mršić 1991).

***Cernosvitovia dudichi* Zicsi & Šapkarev, 1982**

Cernosvitovia dudichi Zicsi & Šapkarev, 1982: 181.
Cernosvitovia (*Zicsiona*) *dudichi*: Mršić 1991: 149. Šapkarev 1997: 103.
Cernosvitovia dudichi: Trakić *et al.* 2016: 259.

Distribution. Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Cernosvitovia getica* (Pop, 1947)**

Allolobophora dugesi v. *getica* Pop, 1947: 8.
Cernosvitovia (*Zicsiona*) *getica*: Mršić 1991: 152. Šapkarev 1997: 103.
Eophila getica: Šapkarev 2002: 302.
Cernosvitovia getica: Csuzdi & Pop 2007: S20 (for complete synonymy). Trakić *et al.* 2016: 259.

Distribution. Romania, Serbia (Mršić 1991).

?*Cernosvitovia knazevensis* (Šapkarev, 1989)

Italobalkaniona knazevensis Šapkarev, 1989: 38.; 1997: 103. Mršić 1991: 173.

Distribution. Serbia (Mršić 1991).

Remarks. The exact position of the male pore is not stated in the original description. Šapkarev (1989) only mentions that it is invisible. Therefore, inclusion of this species to *Cernosvitovia* is uncertain.

***Cernosvitovia krainensis* (Šapkarev, 2002)**

Eophila opisthocystis krainensis Šapkarev, 2002: 303.

Italobalkaniona opisthocystis krainensis: Mršić 1991: 172. Šapkarev 1997: 103.

Cernosvitovia krainensis: Csuzdi 2012. Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 639. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 259.

Distribution. Romania, Serbia (Mršić 1991).

Remarks. This species was formally described in 2002 but appeared in the literature as early as 1991 (Mršić 1991: 172) referring to a manuscript in press which actually has never been published. *C. krainensis* differs from *knazevensis* only in the number and position of spermathecae (7 vs. 5 pairs in 14–20 vs. 12–16). However, *C. knazevensis* was presumably described from a preadult specimen, therefore the synonymy of the two species' names as suggested by Csuzdi (2012) is possible, but requires further corroboration by examining fully adult specimens of *knazevensis*.

***Cernosvitovia munteniana* Zicsi & Pop, 1991**

Cernosvitovia munteniana Zicsi & Pop, 1991: 125. Mršić 1992: 22. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 259. Valchovski & Szedlerjesi 2016: 357.

Distribution. Romania, Bulgaria (Valchovski & Szedlerjesi 2016).

***Cernosvitovia opisthocystis* (Rosa, 1895)**

Allolobophora opisthocystis Rosa, 1895: 4.
Italobalkaniona opisthocystis: Mršić 1991: 170. Šapkarev 1997: 103.
Cernosvitovia (*Zicsiona*) *crnicae*: Mršić 1991: 155. Šapkarev 1997: 103.

Distribution. Romania, Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Cernosvitovia rebeli* (Rosa, 1897)**

Allolobophora rebelii Rosa, 1897: 2.
Cernosvitovia (*Cernosvitovia*) *rebeli*: Mršić 1991: 148. Šapkarev 1997: 103.
Cernosvitovia rebeli: Dhora 2010: 82. Szedlerjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 263. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10.; 2013: 639. Valchovski 2012: 91. Szedlerjesi 2013b: 78. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 260. Szedlerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 62.

Distribution. Romania, Bulgaria, Greece, Albania (Mršić 1991).

***Cernosvitovia schweigeri* (Zicsi, 1973)**

Allolobophora schweigeri Zicsi, 1973: 226.
Cernosvitovia schweigeri: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 8.
Mısırlioğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlioğlu 2009: 22.
Cernosvitovia (Cernosvitovia) schweigeri: Šapkarev 1997: 103.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

Genus *Dendrobaena* Eisen, 1873

***Dendrobaena* sp.**

Dendrobaena byblica byblica: Szederjesi *et al.* 2014a: 558.

Distribution. European part of Turkey (Szederjesi *et al.* 2017b).

Remarks. Only two characters separate this species from *D. byblica*: the number of the seminal vesicles (3 vs. 4) and the position of the tubercles (1/n 25, 26–1/229 vs. 26–28).

***Dendrobaena alexandrii* Szederjesi, Pavlíček & Csuzdi, 2013**

Dendrobaena alexandrii Szederjesi, Pavlíček & Csuzdi, 2013a: 392.

Distribution. Jordan (Szederjesi *et al.* 2013a).

***Dendrobaena alpina alpina* (Rosa, 1884)**

Allolobophora alpina Rosa, 1884: 28.
Dendrobaena alpina alpina: Mršić 1991: 627.
Šapkarev 1993: 17. Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 264.; 2015: 112. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 9. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 151. Szederjesi 2013a: 66.; 2013b: 78. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 182. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 62.
Dendrobaena alpina: Šapkarev 2001: 112. Stojanović & Karaman 2005a: 129. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10. Valchovski 2012: 91.
Dendrobaena alpina mavrovensis Šapkarev, 1971: 160.; 1997: 105. Mršić 1991: 630. **syn. nov.**

Distribution. The Alps, the Balkans and the Southern Carpathians (Csuzdi *et al.* 2011).

Remarks. Examining of two syntypes of *D. alpina mavrovensis* housed in HNHM (HNHM/12673) revealed that the openings of the spermathecae are in the dorsomedian line like in case of the nominal subspecies and not in setal line *d*, as Šapkarev (1971) noted it in the original description. Therefore *D. alpina mavrovensis* is regarded as a synonym of *D. alpina alpina*.

***Dendrobaena alpina armeniaca* (Rosa, 1893)**

Allolobophora alpina v. *armeniaca* Rosa, 1893b: 431.

Dendrobaena alpina armeniaca: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 8. Mısırlioğlu *et al.* 2008: 79.. Mısırlioğlu 2009: 22. Szederjesi *et al.* 2014a: 558.

Distribution. Armenia, Turkey (Rosa 1893b, Omodeo & Rota 1989).

***Dendrobaena alpina popi* Šapkarev, 1971**

Dendrobaena alpina popi Šapkarev, 1971: 159.; 1993: 17.; 1997: 105. Mršić 1991: 634. Csuzdi *et al.* 2011: 13. Pop *et al.* 2012: 63. Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 264. Szederjesi 2013a: 66.

Distribution. Romania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Macedonia, Montenegro, Albania (Csuzdi *et al.* 2011, Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b).

***Dendrobaena attemsi* (Michaelsen, 1902)**

Helodrilus (Dendrobaena) attemsi Michaelsen, 1902: 47.

Dendrobaena attemsi: Mršić 1991: 604. Šapkarev 1993: 17.; 2001: 112.; 2002: 295. Stojanović & Karaman 2005a: 129. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 8. Mısırlioğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlioğlu 2009: 22. Valchovski 2012: 91. Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 264.; 2015: 112. Stojanović *et al.* 2012:10.; 2013: 639. Pop *et al.* 2012: 62. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 9. Szederjesi 2013a: 66.; 2013b: 79. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 62.

Dendrobaena attemsi attemsi: Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 182.

Dendrobaena jastrebensis Mršić & Šapkarev, 1987: 69. Mršić 1991: 583. Šapkarev 1993: 17.; 1997: 105. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 152. Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 639.; 2017a: 183. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 260.

- Dendrobaena macedonica* Mršić, 1991: 587. Šapkarev 1997: 105. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 262.
Dendrobaena vranicensis Mršić, 1991: 588. Šapkarev 1997: 105. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 263.
Dendrobaena grmecensis: Mršić, 1991: 593. Šapkarev 1997: 105.

Distribution. From the Pyrenees through the Balkans and Anatolia to the Caucasus (Omodeo & Rota 1999), but it has been introduced to several regions as well (Blakemore 2008).

Remarks. *D. attemsi* is morphologically highly variable. Its colour varies from overall dark red to red just at the head on dorsum. Also its tubercles are in variable position from 30–31, 1/n32, 1/232, 32 therefore Csuzdi (2012) suggested to synonymize *grmecensis*, *jastrebensis*, *macedonica* and *vranicensis* to *D. attemsi*.

D. attemsi is easily identified apart from the clitellar organs by its last pair of hearts in segment 9 or 10 and the regularly alternating nephridiopores. Unfortunately neither of these two characters were mentioned in the description of the four species synonymized.

***Dendrobaena balcanica* (Černosvitov, 1937)**

- Eisenia veneta* var. *balcanica* Černosvitov, 1937a: 81.
Dendrobaena balcanica: Mršić 1991: 620. Šapkarev 1997: 105. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10. Valchovski 2012: 92. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 260. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 62.

Distribution. Bulgaria, Greece (Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012a).

***Dendrobaena bokakotorensis* Šapkarev, 1975**

- Dendrobaena bokakotorensis* Šapkarev, 1975c: 4.; 1993: 17.; 1997: 105. Mršić 1991: 565. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 151. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 260. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 63.

Distribution. Croatia, Montenegro, Greece (Mršić 1991).

***Dendrobaena bosniaca* Mršić, 1988**

- Dendrobaena bosniaca* Mršić, 1988: 14. 1991: 586. Šapkarev 1997: 105. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 260.

Distribution. Bosnia-Herzegovina (Mršić, 1991, Trakić *et al.* 2016).

***Dendrobaena bruna* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

- Dendrobaena bruna* Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 196. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 8. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrobaena byblica byblica* (Rosa, 1893)**

- Allolobophora* (*Dendrobaena*) *byblica* Rosa, 1893a: 4.
Dendrobaena byblica: Mršić 1991: 566. Šapkarev 1993: 17.; 2001: 113. Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 140. Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 456. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 56.; 2005a: 129. Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2005a: 72. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006b: S114; 2008: 193; 2017: 598. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Dhora 2010: 82. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10.; 2013: 639.; 2017a: 183. Valchovski 2012: 92. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017b: in press.
Dendrobaena byblica byblica: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 8.; 2007: 350. Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 265.; 2015: 112. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 10. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 151. Szederjesi 2013a: 67.; 2013b: 79.; 2014: 49.; Szederjesi *et al.* 2013a: 394.; 2013b: 203.; 2014a: 558.; 2017a: 63.

Distribution. widely distributed in the Mediterranean (Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2017).

***Dendrobaena cevdeti* Szederjesi, Pavlíček, Coşkun & Csuzdi, 2014**

- Dendrobaena cevdeti* Szederjesi, Pavlíček, Coşkun & Csuzdi 2014: 561.

Distribution. Turkey (Szederjesi *et al.* 2014a).

***Dendrobaena cognettii* (Michaelsen, 1903)**

Helodrilus cognettii Michaelsen, 1903: 140.
Dendrobaena cognettii: Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 10. Szederjesi 2013a: 67. Szederjesi *et al.* 2014a: 558.; 2017a: 63.
Dendrobaena pygmaea: Mršić 1991: 643.

Distribution. From Western Europe through the Balkans to Turkey (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Dendrobaena decipiens* (Michaelsen, 1910)**

Helodrilus alpinus decipiens Michaelsen, 1910b: 33.
Dendrobaena decipiens: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 10. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey, Georgia (Omodeo & Rota 1989).

***Dendrobaena depressa* (Rosa, 1893)**

Allolobophora platyura depressa Rosa, 1893b: 543.
Fitzingeria platyura depressa: Mršić 1991: 543. Šapkarev 1993: 17. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11. Valchovski 2012: 95. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 13. Szederjesi 2013a: 70. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308.
Fitzingeria viminiana: Mršić 1991: 539. Šapkarev 1993: 17.; 1997: 104. (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003)
Dendrobaena depressa: Szederjesi *et al.* 2017b: in press.

Distribution. From Austria through the Carpathian Basin to Macedonia and Bulgaria (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Dendrobaena epirotica* Zicsi & Michalis, 1993**

Dendrobaena epirotica Zicsi & Michalis, 1993: 306. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 261. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 64.

Distribution. Greece (Zicsi & Michalis 1993).

***Dendrobaena feheri* Szederjesi & Csuzdi, 2017**

Dendrobaena feheri Szederjesi & Csuzdi, 2017 in: Szederjesi *et al.* 2017b: in press.

Dendrobaena ganglbaueri (part.): Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 265.

Distribution. Albania (Szederjesi *et al.* 2017b).

***Dendrobaena fridericae fridericae* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Dendrobaena fridericae Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 186. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 10. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrobaena fridericae uludagi* Omodeo & Rota, 1991**

Dendrobaena fridericae uludagi Omodeo & Rota, 1991: 179. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 10. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrobaena ganglbaueri* (Rosa, 1894)**

Allolobophora ganglbaueri Rosa, 1894: 1.
Dendrobaena byblica: Mršić 1991: 566. (part.)
Dendrobaena ganglbaueri: Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 265. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 10. Szederjesi 2013a: 67. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017b. in press.

Distribution. Hungary, Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Serbia (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Dendrobaena hamzalensis* Mršić, 1991**

Dendrobaena hamzalensis Mršić, 1991: 639. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 261.

Distribution. Macedonia (Mršić 1991).

***Dendrobaena hauseri* Zicsi, 1973**

Dendrobaena hauseri Zicsi, 1973: 222. Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 456. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 10. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013b: 203.

Distribution. Turkey, Israel (Pavlíček *et al.* 2003).

***Dendrobaena hortensis* (Michaelsen, 1890)**

Allolobophora subrubicunda var. *hortensis* Michaelsen, 1890: 15.

Dendrobaena hortensis: Mršić 1991: 622. Šapkarev 1993: 17.; 2002: 296. Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 456. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 10. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Dhora 2010: 82. Stojanović *et al.* 2012:10.; 2013: 639.; 2017a: 183. Szederjesi 2013b: 79.; 2015: 146.; 2016. Valchovski 2012: 92. Szederjesi *et al.* 2014a: 558.; 2017a: 64.

Dendrobaena pseudohortensis Šapkarev, 1977b: 37.; 1993: 17.; 1997: 105. Mršić 1991: 625. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 262.

Dendrobaena slovenica Mršić, 1991: 640. Šapkarev 1997: 105.

Dendrobaena veneta ochridana: Šapkarev 1993: 17.

Dendrobaena ochridana: Šapkarev 1997: 105.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

Remarks. *D. hortensis* is a highly variable peregrine species originally described with three pairs of vesicles in 9, 11, 12. The morphologically similar species (*D. v. ochridana* Šapkarev, 1993 and *D. slovenica* Mršić, 1991) described with two pairs of vesicles in 11, 12 were put in synonymy by Csuzdi (2012). *D. pseudohortensis* with 3–4 pairs of vesicles was synonymized by Csuzdi & Zicsi (2003).

***Dendrobaena hrabei* (Černosvitov, 1934)**

Eisenia veneta var. *hrabei* Černosvitov, 1934a: 72.

Dendrobaena hrabei: Mršić 1991: 631. Šapkarev 1997: 105. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10. Valchovski 2012: 92. Szederjesi 2013a: 68. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 261. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 64.

Distribution. Bulgaria, Greece, Macedonia (Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a).

***Dendrobaena illyrica* (Cognetti, 1906)**

Helodrilus (Dendrobaena) illyricus Cognetti, 1906: 1.

Dendrobaena illyrica: Mršić 1991: 599. Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 639. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 11.

Distribution. Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Dendrobaena jahorensis* Mršić, 1991**

Dendrobaena jahorensis Mršić, 1991: 585. Šapkarev 1997: 105. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 261.

Distribution. Bosnia-Herzegovina (Mršić 1991).

***Dendrobaena kervillei* (Michaelsen, 1910)**

Helodrilus (Eisenia) venetus var. *kervillei* Michaelsen, 1910a: 166.

Dendrobaena kervillei: Csuzdi & Pavliček 2002: 110. Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 456. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013b: 203.

Distribution. Israel, Lebanon, Syria (Pavliček *et al.* 2003).

***Dendrobaena kozuensis* Šapkarev, 1971**

Allolobophora kozuensis Šapkarev, 1971: 155.

Dendrobaena kozuensis: Mršić 1991: 564. Šapkarev 1993: 17.; 1997: 105. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 152. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 261.

Distribution. Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Dendrobaena loebli* (Zicsi, 1985)**

Fitzingeria loebli Zicsi, 1985a: 330. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 20. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 69.

Fitzingeria loebli: Šapkarev 1997: 105. (sic!)

Fitzingeria loeblii: Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. (sic!)

Dendrobaena loebli: Szederjesi *et al.* 2017b: in press.

Distribution. Turkey, Greece (Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012a).

***Dendrobaena luraensis* Szederjesi & Csuzdi, 2012**

Dendrobaena luraensis Szederjesi & Csuzdi, 2012b: 266. Szederjesi 2014: 50. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 261.

Distribution. Albania, Montenegro (Szederjesi 2014).

***Dendrobaena mahnerti* Zicsi, 1974**

Dendrobaena mahnerti Zicsi, 1974: 449. Mršić 1991: 645. Šapkarev 1997: 105. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 262. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 64.

Distribution. Greece (Mršić 1991).

***Dendrobaena mahunkai* Csuzdi, Pavlíček & Mısırlıoğlu, 2007**

Dendrobaena mahunkai Csuzdi, Pavlíček & Mısırlıoğlu, 2007: 351. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Hatay) (Csuzdi *et al.* 2007).

***Dendrobaena michalisi* Karaman, 1972**

Dendrobaena michalisi Karaman, 1972b: 112. Mršić 1991: 636. Šapkarev 1997: 105. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 262. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 64.

Distribution. Greece (Mršić 1991).

***Dendrobaena montana* (Michaelsen, 1910)**

Helodrilus veneta montana Michaelsen, 1910b: 30. *Dendrobaena montana*: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 10. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrobaena montenegrina* Mršić, 1988**

Dendrobaena montenegrina Mršić, 1988: 19.; 1991: 595. Šapkarev 1997: 105. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 153. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 262.

Distribution. Montenegro (Mršić 1991).

***Dendrobaena negevis* Csuzdi & Pavlíček, 1999**

Dendrobaena negevis Csuzdi & Pavlíček, 1999: 482. Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 456. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006a: 184. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013a: 394.; 2013b: 203.

Distribution. Israel, Jordan (Pavlíček *et al.* 2003).

***Dendrobaena nevoi* Csuzdi & Pavlíček, 1999**

Dendrobaena nevoi Csuzdi & Pavlíček, 1999: 480. Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 456. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013b: 204.

Distribution. Israel (Pavlíček *et al.* 2003).

***Dendrobaena nivalis* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Dendrobaena nivalis Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 190. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 11. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Szederjesi *et al.* 2014a: 559.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrobaena octaedra* Savigny, 1826**

Enterion octaedrum Savigny, 1826: 183. *Dendrobaena octaedra*: Mršić 1991: 607. Šapkarev 1993: 17. Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 139. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 55.; 2005a: 130. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10.; 2013: 639.; 2017a: 183. Valchovski 2012: 93. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 11. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 153.; 2014: 308. Szederjesi 2013a: 68.; 2013b: 79.; 2014: 50. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 65.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Dendrobaena olympiaca* (Michaelsen, 1902)**

Helodrilus ganglbaueri olympiaca Michaelsen, 1902: 45. *Dendrobaena byblica*: Mršić 1991: 566. (part.) *Dendrobaena byblica olympiaca*: Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012a: 32. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 260. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 63. *Dendrobaena olympiaca*: Szederjesi *et al.* 2017b: in press.

Distribution. Greece (Szederjesi 2015).

***Dendrobaena olympica* Černositov, 1938**

Eisenia olympica Černositov, 1938b: 193. *Dendrobaena olympica*: Mršić 1991: 637. Šapkarev 1997: 105. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 262. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 65.

Dendrobaena olimpica: Šapkarev 1993: 17.
Dendrobaena olympica peristerica Šapkarev, 2001:
113.; 1997: 105. **syn. nov.**

Distribution. Greece, Macedonia (Mršić 1991).

Remarks. *Dendrobaena olympica peristerica* described by Šapkarev (2001) differs from the nominal subspecies only in the position of the dorsal pores, the body size and the setal arrangement. However, these characters usually show some degree of variation, therefore *D. olympica peristerica* is regarded as a synonym of *D. olympica olympica*.

***Dendrobaena omodeoi* Csuzdi, Pavlíček & Mısırlıoğlu, 2007**

Dendrobaena omodeoi Csuzdi, Pavlíček & Mısırlıoğlu, 2007: 352. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2014a: 559.

Distribution. Turkey (Hatay) (Csuzdi *et al.* 2007).

***Dendrobaena orientalis orientalis* Černositov, 1940**

Dendrobaena orientalis Černositov, 1940: 444. Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 456. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 11.; 2007: 350. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2013b: 204.; 2014a: 559.

Distribution. Turkey, Israel, Lebanon (Pavlíček *et al.* 2003).

***Dendrobaena orientalis karak* Csuzdi & Pavlíček, 2005**

Dendrobaena orientalis karak Csuzdi & Pavlíček, 2005a: 73.

Distribution. Jordan (Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2005a).

***Dendrobaena orientaloidea* (Zicsi, 1985)**

Dendrobaena alpina orientaloidea Zicsi, 1985a: 326.

Dendrobaena orientaloidea: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 11. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 79. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2014a: 559.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrobaena pantaleonis* (Chinaglia, 1913)**

Helodrilus (Bimastus) pantaleonis Chinaglia, 1913: 5.

Dendrobaena pantaleonis pantaleonis: Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 268.

Dendrobaena pantaleonis eutypica Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 184. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 11. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Dendrobaena pantaleonis balagnensis: Mršić 1991: 642. Šapkarev 1997: 105.

Dendrobaena pantaleonis: Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006b: S114.; 2017: 595. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 65.

Distribution. France, Italy, Albania, Greece, Turkey, Cyprus (Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a).

***Dendrobaena pentheri* (Rosa, 1905)**

Allolobophora (Notogama) pentheri Rosa, 1905: 1.

Dendrobaena pentheri: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 12. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006b: S114; 2008: 193; 2017: 596. Csuzdi *et al.* 2007: 350. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2014a: 560.; 2016.; 2017a: 65.

Dendrobaena aegea (Cognetti, 1913): Mršić 1991: 647. Šapkarev 1997: 105. (Szedzerjesi 2015).

Distribution. Greece (Rhodes), Turkey, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Iran, Cyprus (Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a).

***Dendrobaena persimilis* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Dendrobaena persimilis Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 193. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 12. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrobaena perula* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Dendrobaena perula Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 195. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 12. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrobaena pindonensis* Zicsi & Michalis, 1993**

Dendrobaena pindonensis Zicsi & Michalis, 1993: 307. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 262. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 66.

Distribution. Greece (Zicsi & Michalis 1993).

***Dendrobaena platyura* (Fitzinger, 1833)**

Enterion platyurum Fitzinger, 1833: 533.

Fitzingeria platyura platyura: Mršić 1991: 542. Šapkarev 1993: 17. Stojanović & Karaman 2005a: 130. Szedzerjesi 2013a: 70. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 185.

Dendrobaena platyura: Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017b: in press.

Distribution. Austria, the Carpathian Basin and the Balkans to Macedonia and Bulgaria (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Dendrobaena proandra* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Dendrobaena proandra Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 193. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 12. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrobaena resslı* Zicsi, 1973**

Dendrobaena resslı Zicsi, 1973: 220. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 14. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrobaena retrosella* Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi, 2012**

Dendrobaena retrosella Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi, 2012a: 33. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 262. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 66.

Distribution. Greece (Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a).

***Dendrobaena rhodopensis* (Černosvitov, 1937)**

Eisenia rhodopensis Černosvitov, 1937a: 82.

Dendrobaena rhodopensis: Mršić 1991: 617. Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 140. Šapkarev 1997: 105. Stojanović & Karaman 2003: 56. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10.; 2013: 639. Valchovski 2012: 93. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 153. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 263. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 66.

Dendrobaena durmitorensis Mršić, 1988: 15. Mršić 1991: 617. Šapkarev 1993: 17.; 1997: 105. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 152. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 260.

Distribution. Bulgaria, Greece, Montenegro, Serbia (Mršić 1991).

Remarks. *D. rhodopensis* was first described from Bulgaria. Later Mršić (1988) described a similar species from Durmitor Mts. Montenegro, thought to be differing from *D. rhodopensis* in the position of the spermathecae. According to Mršić (1988) the spermathecae of *D. rhodopensis* open in setal line *d* while those of *D. durmitorensis* near to the mediodorsal line. However, in the original description Černosvitov (1937) clearly states that the spermathecae "münden... dicht neben der dorsalen Medianlinie". Consequently *D. durmitorensis* was regarded as a synonym of *D. rhodopensis* (Csuzdi 2012). Before synonymization, *D. rhodopensis* was recorded even from the Durmitor Mts. by Stojanović & Karaman (2003).

***Dendrobaena rothschildae* Csuzdi & Pavlíček, 1998**

Dendrobaena rothschildae Csuzdi & Pavlíček, 1998: 26. Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 456.

Distribution. Israel (Pavlíček *et al.* 2003).

***Dendrobaena samarigera* (Rosa, 1893)**

Allolobophora samarigera Rosa, 1893a: 5.

Dendrobaena samarigera: Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 456. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 14. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2013b: 204.

Distribution. ?Turkey, Israel, Lebanon (Pavlíček *et al.* 2003).

***Dendrobaena schmidti marinae* Kvadadze, 1985**

Dendrobaena schmidti marinae Kvadadze, 1985: 129. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 14. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Georgia, Turkey (Kvadadze 1985, Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrobaena schmidti tellermanica* Perel, 1966**

Dendrobaena schmidti tellermanica Perel, 1966: 163. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 14. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Dendrobaena surbiensis: Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Dagestan, Turkey (Kvadadze 1985, Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrobaena semitica* (Rosa, 1893)**

Allolobophora semitica Rosa, 1893a: 3.

Dendrobaena semitica: Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 456. Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2005a: 73. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 14.; 2007: 351. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006a: 184.; 2006b: S114.; 2017: 597. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2013a: 395.; 2013b: 204.; 2014a: 560.; 2016.

Distribution. Turkey (Hatay), Cyprus, Israel, Lebanon, Syria, Jordan (Pavlíček *et al.* 2003).

***Dendrobaena serbica* Karaman, 1973**

Dendrobaena serbica Karaman, 1973: 178.; Mršić 1991: 603. Šapkarev 1993: 17.; 1997: 105. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 263. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 183.

Distribution. Serbia, Montenegro (Szedzerjesi 2014).

***Dendrobaena skipetarica* Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi, 2017**

Dendrobaena skipetarica Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi, 2017 in: Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017b.

Dendrobaena ganglbaueri (part.): Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 265.

Distribution. Albania (Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi 2012b).

***Dendrobaena szalokii* Szedzerjesi, Pavlíček, Coşkun & Csuzdi 2014**

Dendrobaena szalokii Szedzerjesi, Pavlíček, Coşkun & Csuzdi, 2014: 561.

Distribution: Turkey (Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2014a).

***Dendrobaena transjordanica* Szedzerjesi, Pavlíček & Csuzdi, 2013**

Dendrobaena transjordanica Szedzerjesi, Pavlíček & Csuzdi, 2013a: 395.

Distribution. Jordan (Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2013a).

?*Dendrobaena vej dovskyi* (Černosvitov, 1935)

Bimastus vej dovskyi Černosvitov, 1935: 66.

Dendrobaena vej dovskyi: Mršić 1991: 592. Milutinović *et al.* 2010: 630. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 183.

Distribution. Austria, Germany, Slovakia, Hungary (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003), ?Serbia.

Remarks. According to our present knowledge *D. vej dovskyi* is a typical Eastern-Alpine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003). Its occurrence in Serbia needs further corroboration.

***Dendrobaena veneta* (Rosa, 1886)**

Allolobophora veneta Rosa, 1886: 674.

Dendrobaena veneta: Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2002: 111. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006a: 184.; 2017: 596. Dhora 2010: 82. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 10.; 2013: 639. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2016.

Dendrobaena veneta veneta: Mršić 1991: 613. Šapkarev 1993: 17. Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 141. Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 456. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 56. Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2005a: 75. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 15.; 2007: 354. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006b: S114.; 2008: 194. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 268. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 11. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 154. Szedzerjesi 2013a: 69.; 2013b: 79.; 2014: 50. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2013a: 396.; 2013b: 205.; 2014a: 560.; 2017a: 66. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 183.

Distribution. Widely introduced peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Dendrobaena zicsi* Karaman, 1973**

Dendrobaena zicsi Karaman, 1973: 178.
Dendrobaena zicsii: Mršić 1991: 590. Šapkarev 1993: 17.; 1997: 105. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 263.

Distribution. Serbia (Mršić 1991).

Genus *Dendrodriloides* Kvavadze, 2000

***Dendrodriloides grandis grandis* (Michaelsen, 1907)**

Eisenia grandis Michaelsen, 1907: 87.
Eophila grandis grandis: Omodeo 1988: 77.
Eisenia grandis grandis: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 16. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.
Dendrodriloides grandis grandis: Csuzdi 2012.

Distribution. Georgia, Armenia, Turkey (Kvavadze 1985, Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Dendrodriloides hydrophilicus* (Kvavadze, 1979)**

Eisenia grandis hydrophilica Kvavadze, 1979: 143.
Eisenia hydrophilica: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 18. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.
Dendrodriloides hydrophilicus: Csuzdi 2012.

Distribution. Turkey, Georgia (Omodeo & Rota 1989).

***Dendrodriloides polysegmenticus* (Kvavadze, 1973)**

Eisenia perelae polysegmentica Kvavadze, 1973: 6.
Eophila grandis polysegmentica: Omodeo 1988: 78.
Eisenia grandis polysegmentica: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 18. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.
Dendrodriloides polysegmenticus: Csuzdi 2012.

Distribution. Turkey, Georgia (Omodeo & Rota 1989).

Genus *Eisenia* Malm, 1877

***Eisenia ariadne* (Michaelsen, 1928)**

Eophila ariadne Michaelsen, 1928: 289.

Dendrobaena ariadne: Šapkarev 1997: 105.

Eisenia ariadne: Trakić *et al.* 2016: 263. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 67.

Distribution. Greece (Naxos) (Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a).

***Eisenia colchidica* (Perel, 1967)**

Eiseniella colchidica Perel, 1967: 101. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 18. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Eisenia colchidica: Mršić 1991: 507. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 67.

Distribution. Georgia, Turkey (Omodeo & Rota 1991).

***Eisenia ebneri* (Michaelsen, 1914)**

Helodrilus venetus var. *ebneri* Michaelsen, 1914: 8.
Eisenia grandis ebneri: Mršić 1991: 509. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Eisenia ebneri: Trakić *et al.* 2016: 263. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 68.

Distribution. Greece (Mršić 1991)

***Eisenia fetida* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion fetidum Savigny, 1826: 182.

Eisenia foetida: Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 140. Šapkarev 2001: 111. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 57. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Eisenia fetida: Mršić 1991: 497. Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 456. Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2005a: 75.; 2005b: 91. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2008: 194.; 2017: 592. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11.; 2013: 640.; 2017a: 184. Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 269. Valchovski 2012: 94.; 2014: 4. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 13. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 155.; 2014: 308. Szedzerjesi 2013a: 69.; 2014: 50. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2014a: 565.; 2016; 2017a: 68. Valchovski & Szedzerjesi 2016: 358.

Eisenia andrei (Bouché, 1972): Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 12. Valchovski & Szedzerjesi 2016: 357.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Eisenia kattoulasi* Zicsi & Michalis, 1981**

Eisenia kattoulasi Zicsi & Michalis, 1981: 254. Mršić 1991: 508. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Csuzdi *et al.*

al. 2006: 18. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 68.

Distribution. Greece, Turkey (Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a).

***Eisenia lucens* (Waga, 1857)**

Lumbricus lucens Waga, 1857: 161.

Eisenia lucens: Mršić 1991: 500. Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 140. Šapkarev 2001: 111. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 57.; 2005a: 130. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11.; 2013: 640.; 2017a: 184. Valchovski 2012: 94.; 2014: 4. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 13. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 155.; 2014: 308. Szederjesi 2013a: 70.; 2013b: 80.; 2014: 50. Valchovski & Szederjesi 2016: 358.

Distribution. From the Pyrenees through the Alps and the Carpathians to Macedonia and Bulgaria (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Eisenia muranyii* Szederjesi & Csuzdi, 2015**

Eisenia muranyii Szederjesi & Csuzdi, 2015: 112. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 264.

Distribution. Albania (Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2015).

***Eisenia oreophila* Szederjesi & Csuzdi, 2012**

Eisenia oreophila Szederjesi & Csuzdi, 2012a: 36. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 264. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 68.

Distribution. Greece (Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012a).

***Eisenia spelaea* (Rosa, 1901)**

Allolobophora spelaea Rosa, 1901: 36.

Eisenia spelaea: Mršić 1991: 503. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 13. Szederjesi 2013a: 70. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308.

Distribution. Italy, Austria, Hungary, Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Montenegro (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003, Szederjesi 2013a).

***Eisenia storkani* Černosvitov, 1934**

Eisenia rosea storkani Černosvitov, 1934a: 71.

Eisenia grandis storkani: Mršić 1991: 510. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Valchovski 2012: 94.

Eisenia storkani: Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 640. Szederjesi 2013b: 80. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 264.

Distribution. Bulgaria (Valchovski 2012).

Genus *Eiseniella* Michaelsen, 1900

***Eiseniella neapolitana* (Örley, 1885)**

Allurus neapolitanus Örley, 1885: 12.

Eiseniella tetraedra neapolitana: Mršić 1991: 524. Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 456. Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2005a: 76.

Eiseniella neapolitana: Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2005b: 92. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 19.; 2007: 355. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006a: 185.; 2006b: S114.; 2008: 194.; 2017: 594. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013a: 398.; 2013b: 206.; 2017a: 68.

Distribution. From France through Macedonia, Greece and Turkey to Cyprus, Jordan and Dagestan (Pavlíček *et al.* 2003).

***Eiseniella ochridana ochridana* Černosvitov, 1931**

Eiseniella ochridana Černosvitov, 1931a: 97. (part.)

Eiseniella ochridana ochridana: Mršić 1991: 525 (for complete synonymy). Šapkarev 1997: 104. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 264.

Distribution. Macedonia (Mršić 1991).

***Eiseniella ochridana profunda* Černosvitov, 1931**

Eiseniella ochridana f. *profunda* Černosvitov, 1931a: 97.

Eiseniella ochridana profunda: Mršić 1991: 527. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 264.

Distribution. Macedonia (Mršić 1991).

***Eiseniella tetraedra* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion tetraedrum Savigny, 1826: 184.

Eiseniella tetraedra: Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2005b: 91. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 19.; 2007: 355. Szederjesi *et*

al. 2014a: 566.; 2017a: 69. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308. Valchovski & Szederjesi 2016: 358.

Eiseniella tetraedra tetraedra: Mršić 1991: 514. Šapkarev 2001: 112. Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 457. Csuzdi & Pavliček 2005a: 76. Pavliček & Csuzdi 2006b: S114.; 2008: 194.; 2016: 8. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 23. Valchovski 2012: 95.; 2014: 5. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11.; 2013: 640.

Eiseniella tetraedra: Pavliček & Csuzdi 2006a: 185. Dhora 2010: 82. Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 269. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 14. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 155. Szederjesi 2013b: 80. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013a: 398; 2013b: 206. Stojanović *et al.* 2017a: 184.

Eiseniella tetraedra pupa (Eisen, 1874): Mršić 1991: 520. Šapkarev 2001: 112. Valchovski 2012: 95.

Eiseniella tetraedra intermedia Černosvitov, 1934: Mršić 1991: 523.

Eiseniella peleensis Tzelepe, 1943: Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

Genus *Healyella* Omodeo & Rota, 1989

***Healyella baloghi* (Zicsi, 1981)**

Bimastos baloghi Zicsi, 1981a: 435.

Healyella baloghi: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 20. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Healyella boluana* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Healyella boluana Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 176. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 20. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Healyella jordanis* (Csuzdi & Pavliček, 1999)**

Bimastos jordanis Csuzdi & Pavliček, 1999: 471.; 2002: 109. Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 456.

Healyella jordanis: Szederjesi *et al.* 2013b: 206.

Distribution. Israel (Pavliček *et al.* 2003).

***Healyella mariae* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Healyella mariae Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 175. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 20. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Healyella michaelsoni* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Healyella michaelsoni Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 174. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 20. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Healyella naja* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Healyella naja Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 176. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 20. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 81. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Healyella schweigeri* (Zicsi, 1981)**

Bimastos schweigeri Zicsi, 1981a: 434.

Healyella schweigeri: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 22. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 81. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Healyella syriaca* (Rosa, 1893)**

Allolobophora syriaca Rosa, 1893b: 461.

Healyella syriaca: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 22.; 2007: 355. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 81. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013a: 398.; 2013b: 206.; 2014a: 566.

Bimastos syriacus: Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 456.

Distribution. Turkey, Syria, Lebanon, Israel, Jordan, Iran (Pavliček *et al.* 2003, Szederjesi *et al.* 2013a).

***Healyella zapparolii* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Healyella zapparolii Omodeo & Rota 1989: 177. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 22. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 81. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

Genus *Helodrilus* Hoffmeister, 1845

***Helodrilus balcanicus balcanicus* (Černosvitov, 1931)**

Eiseniella balcanica Černosvitov, 1931b: 321.
Helodrilus balcanicus balcanicus: Mršić 1991: 108. Šapkarev 1997: 103. Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 640. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 265. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 70.

Distribution. Serbia, Montenegro, Macedonia, Greece (Mršić 1991).

***Helodrilus balcanicus plavensis* (Karaman, 1972)**

Eiseniella balcanica plavensis Karaman, 1972c: 78.
Helodrilus balcanicus plavensis: Mršić 1991: 110. Šapkarev 1997: 103. Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 640. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 156. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 265.

Distribution. Montenegro, Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Helodrilus cernosvitovianus* (Zicsi, 1967)**

Allolobophora cernosvitoviana Zicsi, 1967: 248.
Helodrilus cernosvitovianus: Mršić 1991: 115. Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 640. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 70.

Distribution. Hungary, Ukraine, Poland, Serbia, Greece (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Helodrilus dinaricus* Mršić, 1991**

Helodrilus dinaricus Mršić, 1991: 108. Šapkarev 1997: 103. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 265.

Distribution. Slovenia (Mršić 1991).

***Helodrilus duhlinskae* Zicsi & Csuzdi, 1986**

Helodrilus duhlinskae Zicsi & Csuzdi, 1986: 119. Mršić 1991: 121. Šapkarev 1997: 103. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11. Valchovski 2012: 95. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 265.

Distribution. Bulgaria (Valchovski 2012).

***Helodrilus italicus* Zicsi, 1985**

Helodrilus italicus Zicsi, 1985b: 284. Mršić 1991: 123.

Helodrilus serbicus: Mršić 1991: 120. Šapkarev 1997: 103. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 266.

Distribution. Italy, Serbia (Mršić 1991).

***Helodrilus jadronensis* Šapkarev, 1989**

Helodrilus jadronensis Šapkarev, 1989: 36.; 1997: 103. Mršić 1991: 108. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 14. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 265.

Distribution. Croatia (Mršić 1991).

***Helodrilus kratochvili* (Černosvitov, 1937)**

Eophila kratochvili Černosvitov, 1937b: 130.
Helodrilus kratochvili: Mršić 1991: 114. Šapkarev 1997: 103. Szederjesi *et al.* 2014c: 182. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 265.

Distribution. Bosnia-Herzegovina (Mršić 1991).

***Helodrilus patriarchalis* (Rosa, 1893)**

Allolobophora patriarchalis Rosa, 1893a: 9.
Helodrilus patriarchalis: Mršić 1991: 119. Šapkarev 1997: 103. Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 457. Csuzdi & Pavliček 2005a: 76.; 2005b: 92. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 22.; 2007: 356. Pavliček & Csuzdi 2006a: 185.; 2006b: S114.; 2017: 596. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 81. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 23. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013a: 398.; 2013b: 207.; 2014a: 566.; 2014c: 184.; 2017a: 71.

Helodrilus colchicus Kvavadze, 2000: 82. (Csuzdi 2012, Szederjesi *et al.* 2014c).

Helodrilus zicsianus Kvavadze, 2000: 83. (Csuzdi 2012, Szederjesi *et al.* 2014c).

Distribution. Greece, Turkey, Cyprus, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Syria, Lebanon, Israel, Jordan, Iran (Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a).

***Helodrilus vagneri* Mršić, 1991**

Helodrilus vagneri Mršić, 1991: 116. Šapkarev

1997: 103. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 266. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 71.

Distribution. Bosnia-Herzegovina, Greece (Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a).

Genus *Lumbricus* Linnaeus, 1758

Lumbricus castaneus Savigny, 1826

Enterion castaneum Savigny, 1826: 180.

Lumbricus castaneus: Mršić 1991: 466. Karaman & Stojanović 2002: 224. Dhora 2010: 82. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 156. Szederjesi 2013a: 71.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

Lumbricus improvisus Zicsi, 1963

Lumbricus improvisus Zicsi, 1963: 75. Mršić 1991: 470. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Distribution. Romania, Serbia, Macedonia (Mršić 1991).

Lumbricus meliboeus Rosa, 1884

Lumbricus meliboeus Rosa, 1884: 21. Mršić 1991: 471. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 16. Milutinović *et al.* 2013: 64. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 156.

Distribution. Italy, Austria, Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Montenegro, Serbia, Bulgaria (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013, Milutinović *et al.* 2013).

Lumbricus polyphemus (Fitzinger, 1833)

Enterion polyphemus Fitzinger, 1833: 552.

Lumbricus polyphemus: Mršić 1991: 473. Karaman & Stojanović 2002: 224. Stojanović & Karaman 2005a: 128. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11.; 2013: 640.; 2017a: 185. Valchovski 2012: 96. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 16. Szederjesi 2013a: 71. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308.

Distribution. From Italy through Hungary, Romania, Slovenia, Croatia and Serbia to Bulgaria (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

Lumbricus rubellus Hoffmeister, 1843

Lumbricus rubellus Hoffmeister, 1843: 187. Mršić 1991: 474. Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 141. Šapkarev 2001: 112. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 56.; 2005a: 130. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 23. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 23. Valchovski 2012: 96.; 2014: 5. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11.; 2013: 640.; 2017a: 185. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 16. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 157.; 2014: 308. Szederjesi 2013a: 71.; 2014: 50. Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2015: 113. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 71.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

Lumbricus terrestris Linnaeus, 1758

Lumbricus terrestris Linnaeus, 1758: 647. Mršić 1991: 481. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 56. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11.; 2013: 640. Valchovski 2012: 96.; 2014: 5. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 157.; 2014: 308. Szederjesi 2013b: 80.; 2014: 50. Valchovski & Szederjesi 2016: 358.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

Genus *Murchieona* Gates, 1978

Murchieona minuscula (Rosa, 1905)

Allolobophora minuscula Rosa, 1905: 38.

Murchieona minuscula: Mršić 1991: 535. Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2002: 108. Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 457. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 23.; 2007: 356. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006b: S114.; 2017: 594. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 81. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 23. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 17. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013b: 207.; 2014a: 567.; 2017a: 71. Valchovski & Mısırlıoğlu 2017: 732.

Distribution. Widely distributed in the Mediterranean (Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2017).

Genus *Octodriloides* Zicsi, 1986

***Octodriloides bolei* Mršić, 1987**

Octodriloides bolei Mršić, 1987b: 88.; 1991: 449.
Šapkarev 1997: 104.; Hackenberger Kutuzović
& Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 17.

Distribution. Slovenia, Croatia (Hackenberger
Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodriloides bosniensis* Mršić, 1991**

Octodriloides bosniensis Mršić, 1991: 455.
Šapkarev 1997: 104. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 266.

Distribution. Bosnia-Herzegovina (Mršić 1991).

***Octodriloides dinaricus* Mršić, 1991**

Octodriloides dinaricus Mršić, 1991: 445. Šap-
karev 1997: 104.

Distribution. Slovenia (Mršić 1991).

***Octodriloides janetscheki* (Zicsi, 1970)**

Octolasion (Octodrilus) janetscheki Zicsi, 1970:
171.

Octodriloides janetscheki: Mršić 1991: 450. Šap-
karev 1997: 104. Hackenberger Kutuzović &
Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 17.

Distribution. Slovenia, Croatia (Hackenberger
Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodriloides kamnensis* (Baldasseroni, 1919)**

Octolasion complanatum f. *kamnensis* Baldasse-
roni, 1919: 1.

Octodriloides kamnensis: Mršić 1991: 458. (part.).
Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Ku-
tuzović 2013: 18.

Octodriloides camnensis: Šapkarev 1997: 104.
(sic!)

Distribution. Slovenia, Croatia (Hackenberger
Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodriloides karawankensis* (Zicsi, 1969)**

Octolasion (Octodrilus) karawankensis Zicsi,
1969: 382.

Octodriloides kamnensis: Mršić 1991: 458
(part.).

Octodriloides karawankensis: Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003:
221.

Distribution. Italy, Austria, Hungary, Slovenia
and Croatia (Mršić 1991, Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

Remarks. *Oc. karawankensis* is a typical
Southern Alpine species. The only occurrence on
the Balkan is from Mršić (1991: 461).

***Octodriloides kovacevici* (Zicsi, 1970)**

Octolasion (Octodrilus) kovacevici Zicsi, 1970:
169.

Octodriloides kovacevici: Mršić 1991: 452. Šap-
karev 1997: 104. Hackenberger Kutuzović &
Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 18. Szederjesi
2013a: 72.

Distribution. Slovenia, Croatia (Hackenberger
Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodriloides marinceki* Mršić, 1987**

Octodriloides marinceki Mršić, 1987b: 91.; 1991:
444. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Trakić *et al.* 2016:
266.

Distribution. Slovenia (Mršić 1991).

***Octodriloides poklonensis* Mršić, 1991**

Octodriloides poklonensis Mršić, 1991: 443.
Šapkarev 1997: 104. Hackenberger Kutuzović
& Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 18. Trakić *et*
al. 2016: 266.

Distribution. Croatia (Hackenberger Kutuzo-
vić & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

Genus *Octodrilus* Omodeo, 1956

***Octodrilus albanicus* Szederjesi & Csuzdi, 2012**

Octodrilus albanicus Szederjesi & Csuzdi, 2012b:
271. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 266.

Distribution. Albania (Szederjesi & Csuzdi
2012b).

***Octodrilus bretscheri* (Zicsi, 1969)**

Octolasion bretscheri Zicsi, 1969: 72.

Octodrilus bretscheri: Mršić 1991: 369. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 18. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 157.

Distribution. Italy, Austria, Croatia, Macedonia, Serbia, Montenegro (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodrilus complanatus* (Dugès, 1828)**

Lumbricus complanatus Dugès, 1828: 289.

Octodrilus complanatus: Mršić 1991: 398. Šapkarev 2002: 305. Karaman & Stojanović 2002: 224. Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 457. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 56.; 2005a: 130. Csuzdi & Pavliček 2005b: 92. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 24. Pavliček & Csuzdi 2006b: S114.; 2008: 194.; 2017: 594. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 81. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22. Dhora 2010: 82. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11.; 2017a: 185. Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 270. Valchovski 2012: 96. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 19. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 158.; 2014: 308. Szederjesi 2013a: 72.; 2013b: 81. Szederjesi *et al.* 2014a: 567.; 2017a: 72.

Distribution. Widely distributed in the whole Mediterranean (Pavliček & Csuzdi 2016).

***Octodrilus croaticus* (Rosa, 1895)**

Allolobophora lissaensis var. *croatica* Rosa, 1895: 5.

Octodrilus croaticus: Mršić 1991: 393. Dhora 2010: 82. Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 279. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 19. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 72.

Distribution. Italy, Austria, Croatia, Albania, Greece (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodrilus kvarnerus* Mršić, 1987**

Octodrilus kvarnerus Mršić, 1987b: 39.; 1991: 385. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 20. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 267.

Distribution. Croatia (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodrilus lissaensis* (Michaelsen, 1891)**

Allolobophora lissaensis Michaelsen, 1891: 18.

Octodrilus lissaensis: Mršić 1991: 381. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 20. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 158. Szederjesi 2013a: 72.; 2014: 51.

Octolasion lissaense: Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 142.

Octolasion lissaense: Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 57.

Distribution. From Italy to Romania and through Slovenia, Croatia to Bosnia-Herzegovina and Montenegro (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodrilus mimus* (Rosa, 1889)**

Allolobophora mima Rosa, 1889: 1.

Octodrilus mimus: Mršić 1991: 411. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 20. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 267.

Octodrilus mima: Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Distribution. Italy, Slovenia, Croatia (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodrilus oesophagus* Mršić, 1991**

Octodrilus oesophagus Mršić, 1991: 388. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 267.

Distribution. Slovenia (Mršić 1991).

***Octodrilus pseudolissaensis* Mršić, 1991**

Octodrilus pseudolissaensis Mršić, 1991: 426. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 21.

Distribution. Croatia (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodrilus pseudotranspadanus* (Zicsi, 1971)**

Octolasion (*Octodrilus*) *pseudotranspadanum* Zicsi, 1971: 227.

Octodrilus pseudotranspadanus: Mršić 1991: 377. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 21.

Distribution. Hungary, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Octodrilus rucneri* (Plisko & Zicsi, 1970)**

Octolasium (Octodrilus) rucneri Plisko & Zicsi, 1970: 454.

Octodrilus rucneri: Mršić 1991: 418. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 21. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 267.

Distribution. Italy, Croatia (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodrilus savinensis* Mršić, 1987**

Octodrilus savinensis Mršić, 1987a: 37.; 1991: 420.

Distribution. Slovenia (Mršić 1991).

***Octodrilus slovenicus* (Karaman, 1972)**

Octolasium mima var. *slovenica* Karaman, 1972a: 102.

Octodrilus slovenicus: Mršić 1991: 428. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 22.

Octodrilus slovenicus: Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Distribution. Slovenia, Croatia (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodrilus tergestinus* (Michaelsen, 1910)**

Octolasium mima var. *tergestina* Michaelsen, 1910a: 73.

Octodrilus tergestinus: Mršić 1991: 417. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 22. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 267.

Distribution. Italy, Slovenia, Croatia (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Octodrilus transpadanus* (Rosa, 1884)**

Allolobophora transpadana Rosa, 1884: 45.

Octodrilus transpadanus: Mršić 1991: 371. Csuzdi & Pavlíček 2005a: 76. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 24.; 2007: 357. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006a: 185. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 81. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 23. Dhora 2010: 82. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11.; 2013: 640.; 2017a: 185. Szederjesi & Csuzdi 2012b: 270.; 2015: 114. Valchovski 2012: 97.; 2014: 6. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 22. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 59.; 2014: 308. Szederjesi 2013a: 72.; 2013b: 81. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013a: 398.; 2014a: 567.; 2017a: 73.

Distribution. From Switzerland, Italy to Turkey (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Octodrilus transpadanoides* Zicsi, 1981**

Octodrilus transpadanoides Zicsi, 1981b: 161.; Mršić 1991: 376.

Distribution. Slovenia (Mršić 1991).

***Octodrilus velebiticus* Mršić, 1991**

Octodrilus velebiticus Mršić, 1991: 404. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 23. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 267.

Distribution. Croatia (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

Genus *Octolasion* Örley, 1885

***Octolasion cyaneum* (Savigny, 1826)**

Enterion cyaneum Savigny, 1826: 181.

Octolasion cyaneum: Mršić 1991: 345. Šapkarev 2002: 304. Pavlíček & Csuzdi 2006b: S114.; 2017: 592. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 23. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Octolasion lacteum* (Örley, 1881)**

- Lumbricus terrestris* var. *lacteus* Örley, 1881: 584.
Octolasion lacteum: Karaman & Stojanović 1995: 141.
Octolasion lacteum: Šapkarev 2001: 111. Stojanović & Karaman 2003b: 56.; 2005a: 130. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 24. Dhora 2010: 82. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11.; 2013: 640.; 2017a: 185. Valchovski 2012: 98.; 2014: 6. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 23. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 159.; 2014: 308. Szedzerjesi 2013a: 72.; 2013b: 81.; 2014: 51. Szedzerjesi & Csuzdi 2015: 114. Valchovski & Szedzerjesi 2016: 358. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 73.
Octolasion tyrtaeum: Mršić 1991: 347. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 23.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

Genus *Perelia* Easton, 1983

***Perelia aharonii* (Stephenson, 1922)**

- Helodrilus* (*Allolobophora*) *aharonii* Stephenson, 1922: 136.
Allolobophora (s.l.) *aharonii*: Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 456.
Perelia aharonii: Csuzdi & Pavliček 2005b: 79.

Distribution. Israel (Pavliček *et al.* 2003).

***Perelia biokovica* (Mršić, 1986)**

- Allolobophora biokovica* Mršić, 1986: 71;
Alpodinaridella (*Dinaridella*) *biokovica*: Mršić 1991: 240. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 24. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 267.

Distribution. Croatia (Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013).

***Perelia galileana* Csuzdi & Pavliček, 2005**

- Perelia galileana* Csuzdi & Pavliček, 2005a: 81. Csuzdi *et al.* 2007: 357. Mısırlıoğlu 2008: 81.; 2009: 23. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2013b: 207.

Distribution. Israel, Turkey (Hatay) (Csuzdi *et al.* 2007).

***Perelia hatayica* Csuzdi, Pavliček & Mısırlıoğlu, 2007**

- Perelia hatayica* Csuzdi, Pavliček & Mısırlıoğlu, 2007: 357. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 81. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 23. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2014a: 567.

Distribution. Turkey (Hatay) (Csuzdi *et al.* 2007).

***Perelia makrisi* Szedzerjesi, Pavliček & Csuzdi, 2016**

- Perelia makrisi* Szedzerjesi, Pavliček & Csuzdi 2016: 159.
Allolobophora nematogena: Pavliček & Csuzdi 2006: S114. (part.)
Perelia nematogena: Pavliček & Csuzdi 2016: 11. (part.)

Distribution. Cyprus (Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2016).

***Perelia nematogena* (Rosa, 1903)**

- Allolobophora nematogena* Rosa, 1903: 11. Šapkarev 2002: 297. Pavliček & Csuzdi 2006b: S114.
Microeophila nematogena (part.): Mršić 1991: 221. Šapkarev 1997: 104.
Perelia nematogena: Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 640. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 24. Stojanović & Milutinović 2013: 159. Pavliček & Csuzdi 2017: 595.
Alpodinaridella (*Alpodinaridella*) *lozniciansa* Mršić, 1987: Mršić 1991: 238. Šapkarev 1997: 104. **syn. nov.**
Perelia lozniciansa: Trakić *et al.* 2016: 268.

Distribution. Italy, Hungary, Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Montenegro, Macedonia, Serbia (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

Remarks. Investigation of a large *Pe. nematogena* material housed in the Hungarian Natural History Museum collected in Italy (HNHM/ 6801, 6805, 6841, 6863, 12805, 12826, 12830, 12811), Hungary (4122, 4132, 4135, 4136, 5403, 9120), Croatia (6494, 6495), Slovenia (6743), Serbia (7642, 12799) and Bosnia-Herzegovina (6673) revealed that the position of the clitellum and the tubercles show a greater variance: (cl.) ½ 24, 25, ½ 25, 26, ½ 26, 27 – 33, ½ 34, 34, ½ 35 and (tb.)

½ 28, 29, ½ 29, 30 – 32, ½ 33, 33, ½ 34. The clitellum and tubercles of *Alpodinaridella lozniciana* described by Mršić (1987) (cl: 25 – ½ 34 and tb: 28 – ½ 32) largely overlap with these value ranges; its other characteristics are completely similar with *Pe. nematogena* as well, including its typical hook-shaped nepridial bladders bearing a terminal ampulla. Therefore, *Alpodinaridella lozniciana* is regarded here as a synonym of *Perelia nematogena*.

On the other hand, in the characters of *Microeophila nematogena* (Rosa, 1903) Mršić (1991: 221) does not mention the existence of an ectal ampulla on the nephridial bladders, therefore we can not decide obviously whether the specimens identified by Mršić as *Microeophila nematogena* belong to *Pe. nematogena* or represent a different species.

***Perelia phoebea* (Cognetti, 1913)**

Helodrilus (*Allolobophora*) *phoebeus* Cognetti, 1913: 2.

Aporrectodea (*Aporrectodea*) *jassyensis phoebea*: Mršić 1991: 320.

Allolobophora nematogena Rosa, 1903: Pavliček & Csuzdi 2006: S114. (part.).

Perelia nematogena: Pavliček & Csuzdi 2017: 595. (part.).

Perelia phoebea: Szederjesi *et al.* 2016: 160.; 2017a: 73. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 268.

Distribution. Greece (Rhodes), Cyprus (Szederjesi *et al.* 2016, 2017a).

***Perelia shamsi* Csuzdi & Pavliček, 2005**

Perelia shamsi Csuzdi & Pavliček, 2005a: 84. Szederjesi *et al.* 2013b: 207.

Distribution. Israel (Csuzdi & Pavliček 2005a).

Genus *Proctodrilus* Zicsi, 1985

***Proctodrilus antipai* (Michaelsen, 1891)**

Allolobophora antipae Michaelsen, 1891: 16.

Proctodrilus antipai antipai: Valchovski 2012: 98.

Proctodrilus antipai: Mršić 1991: 131. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11.; 2017a: 186. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 24. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 74.

Distribution. From France to the Black Sea (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Proctodrilus opisthoductus* Zicsi, 1985**

Proctodrilus opisthoductus Zicsi, 1985b: 147. Mršić 1991: 130. Zicsi & Michalis 1993: 303. Šapkarev 1997: 103. Szederjesi 2013a: 72. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 74.

Distribution. Austria, Slovenia, Serbia, Greece (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

***Proctodrilus tuberculatus* (Černosvitov, 1935)**

Eophila antipae var. *tuberculata* Černosvitov, 1935b: 58.

Proctodrilus tuberculatus: Mršić 1991: 134. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 24. Pavliček & Csuzdi 2006b: S114.; 2008: 194.; 2017: 598. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 81. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 23. Stojanović *et al.* 2013: 640. Hackenberger Kutuzović & Hackenberger Kutuzović 2013: 25. Stojanović & Milutinović 2014: 308. Szederjesi *et al.* 2016.; 2017a: 74.

Proctodrilus tuberculata: Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11.

Proctodrilus antipai tuberculatus: Valchovski 2012: 98.

Distribution. From France and Germany to the Western Caucasus (Csuzdi & Zicsi 2003).

Genus *Spermophorodrilus* Bouché, 1975

***Spermophorodrilus antiquus* (Černosvitov, 1938)**

Allolobophora antiqua Černosvitov, 1938b: 198.

Spermophorodrilus antiquus: Dhora 2010: 82. Stojanović *et al.* 2012: 11. Szederjesi *et al.* 2017a: 74.

Spermophorodrilus antiquus antiquus: Mršić 1991: 532. Šapkarev 1997: 104. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 268.

Spermophorodrilus antiquus bouchei: Mršić 1991: 533. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Spermophorodrilus antiquus michalisi: Mršić 1991: 532. Šapkarev 1997: 104.

Distribution. Albania, Greece, Bulgaria (Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a).

***Spermophorodrilus simsoni* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Spermophorodrilus simsoni Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 172. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 25. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 81. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Spermophorodrilus vignai* Omodeo & Rota, 1989**

Spermophorodrilus vignai Omodeo & Rota, 1989: 171.; Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 25. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 81. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 22.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

**Genus *Trapezonscolex* Qiu & Bouché, 1998
stat. nov.**

Eophila (*Trapezonscolex*) Qiu & Bouché, 1998: 195.

***Trapezonscolex cavazzutii cavazzutii* Omodeo, 1988 comb. nov.**

Eophila cavazzutii Omodeo, 1988: 75.

Eophila cavazzutii cavazzutii: Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 19. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 23.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

***Trapezonscolex cavazzutii pascuorum* Omodeo, 1988 comb. nov.**

Eophila cavazzutii pascuorum Omodeo, 1988: 76. Csuzdi *et al.* 2006: 19. Mısırlıoğlu *et al.* 2008: 80. Mısırlıoğlu 2009: 23.

Distribution. Turkey (Csuzdi *et al.* 2006).

Remarks. Qiu & Bouché (1998) created the subgenus *Trapezonscolex* for *Eo. cavazzutii cavazzutii* and *Eo. c. pascuorum* on the basis of some characters differing from the other *Eophila* species *eg.* the lack of dorsal pores, 2 or 3 pairs of vesicles, the presence of testic sacs.

The original description (Omodeo 1988) does not mention the nephridial bladders, but after investigating Omodeo's specimens, Bouché stated that the orientation of the nephridial bladders of *Eophila* is 'reclinate'. Unfortunately, it did not turn out from the text whether he studied the Turkish *cavazzutii* specimens or *Eo. tellinii* (Rosa, 1988). Examination of one preadult *cavazzutii* specimen in the collection of the Hungarian Natural History Museum (HNHM/7918) collected in Dereh, Vil. Giresun, Turkey, revealed that its nephridial bladders are 'reclinate' which clearly separates this species from *Eo. tellinii* and *Eo. crodabepis* Paoletti, 2016 bearing 'proclinate' bladders (Paoletti *et al.* 2016). Therefore, on the basis of the above mentioned characteristics, separation of the subgenus *Trapezonscolex* from *Eophila* and raising it to genus level is proposed.

Species incertae sedis

***Allolobophora eurytanica* (Tzelepe, 1943)**

Eophila eurytanica Tzelepe, 1943: 1.

Allolobophora eurytanica: Trakić *et al.* 2016: 255. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 76.

Distribution. Greece (Zicsi & Michalis 1981).

Remarks. *A. eurytanica* was described with cl: on 1/230–36 and tb: on 35, 36. It has a large male pore on 15 and two pairs of spermathecae in 9/10–10/11 *d.* The species has never been reported after the original description. The position of the clitellum and the large male pores suggest its similarity to *A. chlorotica*. Normally *A. chlorotica* possesses three pairs of tubercles on 31, 33, 35 however, in anomalous specimens these tubercles can vary in number and position therefore, we

cannot exclude that *eutrytanica* is just an anomalous *A. chlorotica* specimen.

***Dendrobaena sasensis* Šapkarev, 1993**

Dendrobaena sasensis Šapkarev, 1993: 22.; 1997: 105. Mršić 1991: 603. Trakić *et al.* 2016: 263.

Distribution. Macedonia (Mršić 1991).

Remarks. The tubercles of this species are on segments 31–32, in all other characters it resembles *D. attemsi*. As the position of the tubercles can vary within 30–1/n32, 1/232, 32 in case of the latter species, we can't obviously exclude that *D. sasensis* is in fact *D. attemsi* especially if the nephridiopores – which are not mentioned in the original description – alternate regularly.

Family Acanthodrilidae Claus, 1880

Genus *Dichogaster* Beddard, 1888

***Dichogaster bolau* (Michaelsen, 1891)**

Benhamia bolavi Michaelsen, 1891: 9.
Dichogaster bolau: Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 457.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Csuzdi 2010).

Genus *Microscolex* Rosa, 1887

***Microscolex dubius* (Fletcher, 1887)**

Eudrilus dubius Fletcher, 1887: 378.
Microscolex dubius: Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 457.
Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2014a: 568.; 2017a: 75.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Blakemore 2008).

***Microscolex phosphoreus* Dugès, 1837**

Lumbricus phosphoreus Dugès, 1837: 17.
Microscolex phosphoreus: Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 457. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 75.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Blakemore 2008).

Family Criodrilidae Vejdovsky, 1884

Genus *Criodrilus* Hoffmeister, 1845

***Criodrilus lacuum* Hoffmeister, 1845**

Criodrilus lacuum Hoffmeister, 1845: 41. Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 457. Csuzdi *et al.* 2007: 358. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2014a: 568.; 2017a: 74.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Blakemore 2008).

Family Megascolecidae Rosa, 1891

Genus *Amynthas* Kinberg, 1867

***Amynthas corticis* (Kinberg, 1867)**

Perichaeta corticis Kinberg, 1867: 102.
Amynthas corticis: Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 75.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Blakemore 2008).

***Amynthas gracilis* (Kinberg, 1867)**

Nitocris gracilis Kinberg, 1867: 102.
Amynthas gracilis: Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 75.

Distribution. Peregrine species found from tropical to warm-temperate localities (Blakemore 2008).

Genus *Metaphire* Sims & Easton, 1972

***Metaphire californica* (Kinberg, 1867)**

Pheretima californica Kinberg, 1867: 102.
Metaphire californica: Pavliček *et al.* 2003: 457.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Blakemore 2008).

Genus *Pontodrilus* Perrier, 1874

***Pontodrilus litoralis* (Grube, 1855)**

Lumbricus litoralis Grube, 1855: 127.
Pontodrilus litoralis: Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 76.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Blakemore 2008).

Family Ocneroдрilidae Beddard, 1891

Genus *Eukerria* Michaelsen, 1935

Eukerria saltensis (Beddard, 1895)

Kerria saltensis Beddard, 1895: 225.

Eukerria saltensis: Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 76.

Distribution. Widely distributed peregrine species (Blakemore 2008).

Genus *Ocneroдрilus* Eisen, 1878

Ocneroдрilus occidentalis Eisen, 1878

Ocneroдрilus occidentalis Eisen, 1878: 10. Pavlíček *et al.* 2003: 457. Szedzerjesi *et al.* 2017a: 76.

Distribution. Widely distributed pantropical species (Blakemore 2008).

SUMMARY

The first combined checklist of the earthworms of the Balkans, Anatolia, the Levant and Cyprus contains 226 species and subspecies, of which 216 belong to the family Lumbricidae, the dominant family in the Holarctic. The acanthoдрilids take part with three, the megascolecids with four, the ocneroдрilids with two and the crioдрilids with one species.

Altogether 27 species, including all non-lumbricids, are widely distributed peregrines (11.9%). However it's worth to emphasize that some peregrine lumbricid species could also be members of the autochthonous fauna but nowadays it would be difficult to prove this.

Out of the 166 Balkanic species 90 occur solely on the Peninsula (54.2%). Anatolia has 26 endemic species out of the 70 taxa present (37.1%), while Levant has 14 out of the 42 (33.3%). With 21 species present, Cyprus has only one endemic

earthworm, *Perelia makrissi* Szedzerjesi, Pavlíček & Csuzdi, 2016.

The family Lumbricidae is represented with 19 genera, of which *Dendrobaena* is the most speciose with 67 taxa. This clearly confirms the statement of Omodeo & Rota (1989) that this genus has two of its three main distribution centres (Caucasus–Transcaucasus–Anatolia and the Balkan Peninsula–Carpathian Basin) on the area studied.

Studying the literature resulted in finding several synonym names in the region, *e.g.* *Allolobophora kosowensis montenegrina* (= *A. kosowensis kosowensis*), *Dendrobaena alpina mavrovensis* (= *D. alpina alpina*), *D. olympica peristerica* (= *D. olympica olympica*) and *Alpodinaria lozniciana* (= *Perelia nematogena*).

On the basis of the orientation of nephridial bladders ('reclinate'), lack of dorsal pores and the number of seminal vesicles (2 or 3 pairs) we proposed raising the subgenus *Trapezonscolex* to genus level for the former Turkish *Eophila* species *Eo. cavazzutii cavazzutii* and *Eo. cavazzutii pascuorum*.

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